

Effect of Supervisory Roles of School Inspectors on Classroom Teaching in Educational District V of Lagos State Public Secondary School

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Abstract:

This study examined the effects of supervisory practices of school inspectors on classroom teaching in Lagos State Education District V of Lagos State Public Secondary School. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population consisted of all public secondary schools in Lagos State Education District V. The sample comprised 200 respondents from public secondary schools. The simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the sample. This gives equal opportunity for all respondents to be part of the sample. Data was collected with self-developed supervisory roles of School Inspectors on Classroom Teaching (ARSICTQ). Data collected were analysed using frequency count, simple percentages for the demographic data while the inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and Chi-square were used to test all the four hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that school supervisory roles and teacher's performance have a statistically significant linear relationship. The direction of the relationship is positive i.e., greater school supervisory roles are associated with greater teachers' performance. The findings also revealed that school supervisory roles and educational outcome have a statistically significant linear relationship. The direction of the relationship is positive i.e., greater school supervisory roles is associated with greater educational outcome. The results further revealed that there was a significant difference between teacher's performance before and after

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inspector’s supervisory activities in Lagos State Education District V. The result also indicated that there was a difference in school inspector’s supervisory roles and supervisory roles of the school principal in Lagos State Education District V. It can be concluded that supervisory roles of school inspectors play significant roles in the determination of classroom teaching outcome in public secondary school. It was therefore recommended that parents should be ready to give quality attention to the needs of children in order to support their learning.

Keywords: Supervisory Roles, School Inspectors, Classroom Teaching, Educational District, Public Secondary,

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Introduction

The need to provide standard education for all children is one of the major objectives of the race for self-reliance all over the globe (Olofin & Kolawole, 2020). One of the Nigerian national education goals is the attainment of appropriate skills and development of mental, physical and social abilities and competencies as apparatus for the individual to contribute to the development of the society (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). It has been observed that structures in public secondary school have not been seen working due to lack or low level of supervision. Records of action plans, monitoring and follow up reports has been observed that supervision rarely occur in many schools, and in the few schools where it takes place the effect does not seem to show in teacher performance. It has been observed over the years that school supervision is either done to punish teachers or to debar them from promotion in most public secondary schools in Lagos State Education District V. This made teachers not to be comfortable with the in which they are inspected. To promote this laudable role of school inspection in public secondary schools in Lagos State Education Districts V, there is need to examine the effects of supervisory practices of school inspectors on classroom teaching.

Every institution or individual have a set goals and objectives to be achieved. Without a target and set goals, supervision and inspection will be meaningless and supervision and inspection, goals cannot be achieved. In the educational system, there are various reasons for carrying out supervision and inspection in schools. One of these crucial reasons is to ensure that the individual teacher within the school environment will perform his/her obligation as enshrine in the condition of service (Mtormabari & Baridoolenu, 2016).

Supervision has been conceived as the improvement in teaching and learning process for the ultimate benefit of the learner who is regarded as the pivot of education. In the same vein, supervision is essentially a leadership function, a kind of superior subordinate relationship. Where a leader or an officer instructs, oversees and corrects subordinates in order to enhance effective performance. Supervision is needed in effective and efficient school activities; so that educators can really give their best in their various duties posts and as well make extra ordinary contribution to brandishing learners who will be capable of competing globally with their counterparts (Adelakun in Ibidapo, 2019). Supervision of teacher is the means by which subordinate staff of the school are mobilized and motivated towards the full attainment of the goals and objectives of the school they serve. Supervision ensures that the right thing is done through direction and monitoring of teacher activities in school i.e., making checks and balances to some specially assigned duties.

According to Adetula (2010), inspection is an assessment of the state of education system to ascertain its purported standard. It thus indicates that, inspection is a means of monitoring schools' activities to make sure that they are carried out according to standard in such a way that can ensure the attainment of the stated school's objectives and education in general. This is carried out by individual who are known as the inspectors. In Nigeria, inspectors are officers trained in the field of education. They are found in the inspectorate department of the federal and states ministries of education and also in the teaching service commission, area education offices, Local Government Education Authorities (LGEA), State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB), and in other educational service providers. Although, due to the scarcity of qualified personnel many staff of these parastatals are usually co-opted as

inspectors to visit schools. They are concerned with curriculum development, effective utilization of grants and materials allocated to schools, stimulation of teachers and making sure that schools are strictly complying with educational objectives, standards, and policies of government (Ibidapo, 2019).

Secondary schools' system in Lagos State has undergone series of changes in administration. There was a period when the secondary schools were been managed under the voluntary agencies like the Baptist, Roman Catholic, Private Owners and others together with the Local Education Authority. During those days, principals of secondary schools were chosen by the administrative assistance of various agencies and the local education officer. At this period of time no university agreed rules and policy exists, in such voluntary agency has her own criteria. The principal at that time worked in close relation with the administrative assistance in the running of the secondary school since the quality of an educational system of a country depends to a large extent on the qualities of the leaders, thus the opportunity opens to principals in participating in the teaching and learning format of the school was in adequate as it did not allow for principal's initiatives. The principal plays an important role in determines the kind of personality being those students under his control will be later in the adult life. Therefore, it is advisable for the principal to know those qualities that are expected of them.

Effective supervision of the school ensures proper function and mutual interaction of both human and non-human resources involved in the processing of the child and harmonizes the efforts of all designated school personnel. The adverse effects of supervision may lead to a situation whereby the principal will be subjective instead of been objective. That is, supervision may lead to a situation whereby both the principal and the teachers put in their very best in order to satisfy the supervisor, after which they withdraw their efforts at the end of supervision. This leads to a kind of eye service performance in school.

The study looked into the influence of supervisory practices of school inspectors on classroom teaching in Lagos State Education District V. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- a) investigate the relationship between school supervisory roles and teacher performance in Lagos State Education District V;
- b) examine the relationship between school inspector's supervisory roles and the quality of educational outcomes in Lagos State Education District V;
- c) to find out the difference between teacher's performance before and after inspector's supervisory activities in Lagos State Education District V and;
- d) examine the difference between school inspector's supervisory roles and supervisory roles of the school principal in Lagos State Education District V.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated from the above stated objectives.

1. There is no significant relationship between school supervisory roles and teacher performance in Lagos State Education District V.
2. There is no significant relationship between school inspector's supervisory roles and the quality of educational outcomes in Lagos State Education District V.

3. There is no significant difference between teacher's performance before and after inspector's supervisory activities in Lagos State Education District V.
4. There is no significant difference between school inspector's supervisory roles and supervisory roles of the school principal in Lagos State Education District V.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised all the public secondary schools in Lagos State Education District V. A total of two hundred respondents (200) constituted the sample of the study. The simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the sample. This gives equal opportunity for all respondents to be part of the sample. Data was collected with self-developed supervisory roles of School Inspectors questionnaire on Classroom Teaching (ARSICTQ). The questionnaire was in two sections. Section A focused on demographic information while section B was used to collect information on the variables selected for the study. The questionnaire was a closed ended type designed in line with the modified Likert 4- point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). A total of 200 copies of questionnaire were administered by the researcher with the help of the two research assistants. The entire copies of the questionnaire were administered in one week and retrieved to avoid loss. Data collected were analysed using frequency count, simple percentages for the demographic data while the inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Chi-square were used to test all the four hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between school supervisory roles and teacher performance in Lagos State Education District V.

Table 1: Result of correlation between school supervisory roles and teacher performance in Lagos State Education District V

		School Super Roles	Teacher Performance
School Super Roles	Pearson Correlation	1	.610**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Teacher Performance	Pearson Correlation	.610**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 shows that the correlation of school supervisory roles and teacher performance ($r = 0.610$), based on $n = 100$; $p < 0.05$. Based on the results, we can state there was significant linear relationship between school supervisory roles and teacher's performance ($p < .001$). The direction of the relationship is positive (i.e., school supervisory roles and teachers' performance are positively correlated), meaning that these variables tend to increase together (i.e., greater school supervisory roles is associated with greater teachers' performance).

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between school inspector's supervisory roles and quality of educational outcomes in Lagos State Education District V.

Table 2: Result of correlation between school inspector's supervisory roles and quality of educational outcomes in Lagos State Education District V

	School Super Roles	Educational Outcome
School Super Roles Pearson Correlation	1	.610**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
N	100	100
Educational outcome Pearson Correlation	.571**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
N	100	100

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that the correlation of school supervisory roles and educational outcome ($r = 0.571$), based on $n = 100$; $p < 0.05$. Based on the results, school supervisory roles and educational out have a statistically significant linear relationship ($p < .001$). The direction of the relationship is positive (i.e., school supervisory roles and educational outcome are positive correlated), meaning that these variables tend to increase together (i.e., greater school supervisory roles is associated with greater educational outcome).

Ho3: There is no significant difference between teacher's performance before and after inspector's supervisory activities in Lagos State Education District V.

Table 3: Chi-square (X^2) analysis on difference between teacher's performance before and after inspector's supervisory activities in Lagos State Education District V

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	76.000 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correlation	95.295	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	122.173	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	99.000	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	100				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.00.

b. Computed only for a 2×2 table.

From table 3 above, it could be observed that the Pearson Chi-square statistic $X^2(1) = 76.000$, and p is lesser than 0.05. The null hypothesis which state that there is no difference between teacher's performance before and after inspector's supervisory activities in Lagos State Education District V. This implies that there is difference teacher's performance before and after inspector's supervisory activities in Lagos State Education District V.

Ho4: There is no significant difference in school inspector's supervisory roles and supervisory roles of the school principal in Lagos State Education District V.

Table 4: Chi-square (X^2) analysis on difference between school inspector's supervisory roles and supervisory roles of the school principal in Lagos State Education District V

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	95.392 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correlation	90.839	1	.000		

Likelihood Ratio	113.337	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	94.438	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	100				

- a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.30.
b. Computed only for a 2 × 2 table.

From the table four above, it could be observed that the Pearson Chi-square statistics X^2 (1) 95.392 and p is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in school inspector's supervisory roles and supervisory roles of the school principal in Lagos State Education District V is hereby rejected indicating that there is difference in school inspector's supervisory roles and supervisory roles of the school principal in Lagos State Education District V.

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that there is significant relationship between school supervisory roles and teacher performance in Lagos State Education District. The finding is in support of Archibong (2010) asserts that instructional supervision constitutes the leverage point for instructional improvement, teacher's competence and efficiency of the educational system while an unsupervised instruction may mar the standard of education. The findings showed that there is significant relationship between school inspector's supervisory roles and the quality of educational outcome in Lagos State Education District V. This finding is in line with Okendu (2012) which reported that instructional process and supervision help a lot in improving academic performance of students. The findings of this study revealed that there is significant difference between teacher's performance before and after inspector's supervisory activities in Lagos State Education District V. This finding agrees with Kagambe (2004) formative evaluation on the performance of school inspectors in the management of primary schools was conducted in Kabarole District, Uganda.

The findings of the study also revealed that inspectors had ensured that proper account of government grants to schools had been made, that teacher salaries had been disbursed and that the provident fund and retirement benefits had been accounted for. The findings revealed that there is significant difference in school inspector's supervisory roles and supervisory roles of the school principal in Lagos State Education District V. This finding corroborate Namugwanya (2006) conducted on school inspection used by inspectors of schools in Mubende District, Uganda, and the head teachers' and teachers' attitudes toward those techniques in particular and school inspection in general. The study further revealed that head teachers had not been involved in the preparations ahead of inspection, and that inspection lacked a feedback mechanism.

Conclusion

The study concludes that supervisory roles of school inspectors play significant roles in the determination of classroom teaching outcome in public secondary school.

Recommendations

The study recommended that parent should be ready to give quality attention to the physical, social and emotional needs of children through motivation, counseling and guidance in order

to support their learning and enhance their academic performance. Teachers should ensure smooth communication between schools and homes where the pupils reside so as to foster the needed relationship and partnership that will be beneficial to the academic performance of their pupils. Schools should educate parents, especially mothers, so as to develop skills which will complement teachers' skills and expertise.

References

- Achombo, C.N. (2010). Factors affecting the performance of pupils in primary schools in Paidha Town Council. A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Masters of Arts in Educational Management of Makerere University. Retrieved from <http://news.mac.ac.ug/documents/Markfiles/pdf>.
- Ajayi, K.O., Muraino, K.O., & Lewani, A.O. (2011). Parents' education, occupation and real mother's age as predictors of students' achievement in Mathematics in some selected secondary schools in Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of African Studies*, 4(11), 50-60.
- Akinsanya, O.O., Ajayi, K.O., & Salomi, M.O. (2011). Relative effects of Parents' Occupation, Qualification and Academic Motivation of Wards on Students' Achievement in Senior secondary School Mathematics in Ogun State. *British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 3(2).
- Dania, P.O. & Eboh, R.N. (2013). The effects of two instructional sequencing modes on academic achievement of primary social studies in Delta State. *African Journal of Education and Technology*, 3(1): 104-114.
- Hess, R.D. (2010). Social class and ethnic influence upon socialization in PH. Mussen (Ed) Carmichael's manual of child psychology. New York Wiley.
- Makewa, L.N., Role, E., & Otewa, F. (2012). Parental factors affecting academic achievement of Grade six Pupils in Kisumu City, Kenya. *International Journal of Asian Social Science* 2(11): 1984-1997.
- Olofin, S.O. and Kolawole, E.B. (2020). Effect of Kolawole's Problem-Solving Teaching Strategy on the Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Mathematics in Nigeria. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 7(2) 68-77. DoI:10.14738/assrj.72.7749.
- Osiki, J.O. (2011). Effects of remedial training programme on the management of learning acquisition defectiveness and poor study habits problems of selected subjects in a Community Grammar School. *Nigerian Journal of Applied Psychology*, 6(2): 107-115.
- Owen, V. (1999). Exploring Beliefs about Academic Performance Achievement. *The Uganda Education Journal*, 2(57)
- UNESCO, (2010). *Reaching the marginalized Education for all Global Monitoring Reports*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Yusuf, M. A., & Adigun, J.T. (2010). The Influence of School Sex, Location and Type on Students' Academic Performance. *International Journal of Education and Science*, 2(2): 81-85.

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